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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF COMPANIES LISTED ON THE ESG INDEX

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Abstract

As the world struggles with climate change, social inequality, and governance challenges, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) companies have emerged as leaders in sustainable business practices. This study examines the significance of ESG companies in promoting long-term financial performance, risk management, and stakeholder value. A comparative analysis of Random Effects and Fixed Effects models was conducted to assess the relationship between ESG factors and financial performance. The Hausman test confirmed that the Fixed Effects model was appropriate.

Keywords: ESG, sustainability, corporate social responsibility, financial performance, risk management, stakeholder value.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing has emerged as a global phenomenon, gaining widespread acceptance among investors, corporations, and governments. With the rising emphasis on responsible investing, ESG reporting has become indispensable. It furnishes a detailed picture of corporate sustainability, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions that balance financial returns with environmental and social responsibility. India's ESG landscape has witnessed significant growth, driven by key factors such as escalating climate change concerns, investor and regulatory pressure for sustainable practices, and the rising influence of a socially conscious middle class.

ESG is often considered for investor point of view, where as it should also be considered in broader perspective including customers, suppliers and employees who are concerned with organisation

performance. Each aspect of ESG plays an important role in the effort to increase a company's focus on justifiable and proper practices.

Environmental: it involves considerations of overall effect on the environment and potential risks and opportunities it faces because of environmental issues it includes air and water pollution, deforestation, carbon footprint, energy consumption and efficiency, etc.

Social: organization's relationships with stakeholders. It is related as how company treats its employee with reference to fair wages employee engagement work place safety and health, data protection, customer satisfaction level support to human rights and many more

Governance: it is about the organisation how it is managed & guided. How the organizational objective is aligned with stakeholder expectations, how the rights of stakeholders are viewed and respected. What kind of internal control exist to promote transparency and accountability in the

organisation. Board composition, compensation policies, ethical business practices, organisation leadership and management

A NSE group company provides a variety of indices and index related services and products for the Indian capital markets the construct of NIFTY100 ESG indices results in portfolio with similar sector exposure vis-à-vis NIFTY 100 (parent index), but with stock level ESG tilt. This results in portfolio with higher weightage towards companies with better ESG performance. It is designed to reflect the performance of companies that are part of NIFTY 100 index, based on Environmental, Social & Governance score. Companies involved in any ESG controversy

shall not be considered in the index. Companies engaged in tobacco alcohol, controversial weapons and gambling operations shall be excluded. Sector weights are based on free float market capital. Each index constitutes within sector is tilt weighted based on ESG score and is capped at 10%. The indices has a base date of April 1/2011 and base value of 1000.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Zhao, C., Guo, Y., Yuan, J., Wu, M., Li, D., Zhou, Y., & Kang, J. (2018).: In this article, study China's listed power generation groups to explore the relationship between ESG performance and financial indicators in the energy power market based on the panel regression model. The results show that good ESG performance can indeed improve financial performance, which has significant meanings for investors, company management, decisionmakers, and industry regulators

Naeem, N., & Çankaya, S. (2022): ESG performance data and financial data of 192 energy and power generation firms from 2008 to 2019 were taken from Thomson Reuters Eikon database for the statistical analyses. The findings suggest that ESG performance has both positive and significant impacts over the profitability of the firms but negative impact over the market value of the firms. Besides, ESG performance is correlated in a significant way with the financial performance of energy and power generation corporations. This study adds value and importance to the sustainable business practice and sustainability reporting for the energy and power generation companies worldwide

Kalia, D., & Aggarwal, D. (2023). This paper aims to investigate the effect of total and each individual component of environmental, social and governance score (ESG) on financial performance (FP) of healthcare companies. The results of the study suggest that relation between ESG score and FP cannot be generalized. The results show that performing ESG activities positively impact firm performance of healthcare companies in developed economies; however, this relationship would be negative or insignificant in the case of developing economies

Maji, S. G., & Lohia, P. (2023). This paper aims to investigate the impact of environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance on the firm performance of select Indian companies. The present paper is a cross-section study based on secondary data with a sample of 222 Indian firms. The ESG performance for Indian companies is based on the Credit Rating Information Services of India Limited (CRISIL) ESG score, The study reveals that Indian firms focus much more on governance and social parameters than environmental ones. The results indicate that ESG performance and its components are positively associated with firm performance

various studies have been conducted finding the relationship between ESG companies and its financial performance of health care sector, power generation industries and also based on the market data both BSE & NSE.

Objectives: To develop an Econometric model to establish relation between ESG companies and its performance

METHODOLOGY

For the study 10 company from ESG 100 Index from the year 2013 to 2024 were considered. For which Return on asset, leverage and total assets were compiled. All data are collected from Screener in and nifty 100 ESG factsheet top 10 weightage were considered as on 30th

September 2024. Infosys ltd, HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, Bharathi Airtel, HCL, TCS, Tech Mahindra, Tata Motors, Wipro were considered for the study

To achieve this following step are followed:

- Panel unit root testing ensured data stationarity.

- Descriptive statistics summarized variable characteristics.
- Pooled data analysis identified overall relationships.
- Fixed effects modeling controlled for individual-specific effects.
- Random effects modeling verified the findings and assessed model robustness
- To choose between the fixed effects and random effects models, a Hausman test was performed

DATA ANALYSIS AN INTERPRETATION

leverage and size of the company are utilized in this study. Leverage is the use of borrowed funds by a firm. It is measured by the ratio of total assets to net worth. The study uses natural log of total assets as a proxy for size. Data on total assets as well as the net worth is obtained from Prowess database.

Since it was panel data unit root test is conducted to ensure data integrity by using EViews.

Table: 1 unit root test

Panel unit root test: SummarySeries: LEVER
 Date: 10/17/24 Time: 22:26 Sample: 3/01/2013 3/01/2024
 Exogenous variables: Individual effectsUser-specified lags: 1
 Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernelBalanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.*	Cross-sections	Obs
<u>Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)</u>				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-2.33312	0.0098	10	100
<u>Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)</u>				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.94928	0.0256	10	100
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	33.5129	0.0296	10	100
PP - Fisher Chi-square	70.9164	0.0000	10	110
		0		

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. probability is < .05 hence it was found that all the variables are integrated at level it means unit root does not exist.

Descriptive statistics was conducted to examine the variables and it is shown as below:

Table : 2 Descriptive statistics

	ROA	LEVER	LOG01
Mean	0.069176	1.336376	12.44758
Median	0.034655	1.302073	12.57567
Maximum	0.271047	1.994498	15.20933
Minimum	-0.067606	1.028032	9.103200
Std. Dev.	0.071049	0.216978	1.415331
Skewness	0.629771	0.856742	-0.091340
Kurtosis	2.355785	3.443651	2.041783
Jarque-Bera Probability	10.00729	15.66428	4.757757
	0.006713	0.000397	0.092654
Sum	8.301089	160.3651	1493.709
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.600715	5.602478	238.3762
Observations	120	120	120

maximum value on return on asset is .271047 & minimum value is -0.067606 indicates volatility in returns, suggesting that the investment or asset carries risk. Leverage maximum at 1.994498 and minimum at 1.028032. Total assets maximum is at 15.209 & minimum 9.1032

Panel data regression: : Pool data analysis is conducted to identify overall relationship. Panel data is longitudinal data, measuring variables observed for a number of entities across time. While pooled ordinary least square can be used on panel data, it may not provide optimum results.

Table:3 Panel Least Squares

Dependent Variable: ROA Method: Panel Least Squares Date: 10/17/24 Time: 22:30
 Sample (adjusted): 3/01/2013 3/01/2024 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 10
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	0.475219	0.075334	6.308137	0.0000
LOGo1	-0.026947	0.004285	-6.288518	0.0000
LEVER	-0.052846	0.027951	-1.890649	0.0611
R-squared	0.253183	Mean dependent var		0.069176
Adjusted R-squared	0.240417	S.D. dependent var		0.071049
S.E. of regression	0.061922	Akaike info criterion		-2.701184
Sum squared resid	0.448624	Schwarz criterion		-2.631497
Log likelihood	165.0711	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.672884
F-statistic	19.83247	Durbin-Watson stat		0.094185
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

F Statistics is <.05 model is found to be significant. However total asset is less than .05, and leverage is .0611 and R Squared is at .025 which is less than 65% R squared is less than 65%, hence fixed and random effect is to be conducted A fixed effects model is a statistical technique used to control for individual-specific or group- specific variations in panel data.

Table: 4 Fixed Effect Model

Dependent Variable: ROA Method: Panel Least Squares Date: 10/17/24 Time: 22:33
 Sample (adjusted): 3/01/2013 3/01/2024 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 10
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	0.497770	0.083266	5.978079	0.0000
LEVER	-0.059547	0.029764	-2.000637	0.0480
LOGo1	-0.028039	0.004743	-5.911874	0.0000

Effects Specification

Period fixed (dummy variables)			
R-squared	0.269698	Mean dependent var	0.069176
Adjusted R-squared	0.180132	S.D. dependent var	0.071049
S.E. of regression	0.064333	Akaike info criterion	-2.540212
Sum squared resid	0.438704	Schwarz criterion	-2.215005

Log likelihood	166.4127	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.408144
F-statistic	3.011180	Durbin-Watson stat	0.086690
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000853		

It is found that probability for all variable is less than .05 hence model is significant p-values: indicate statistical significance of coefficients

Table: 5 Radom Effect Model

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel EGLS (Period random effects)Date: 10/17/24 Time: 22:35

Sample (adjusted): 3/01/2013 3/01/2024 Periods included: 12; Cross-sections included: 10; Total panel (balanced) observations: 120; Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	0.475219	0.078267	6.071790	0.0000
LEVER	-0.052846	0.029039	-1.819812	0.0713
LOG01	-0.026947	0.004452	-6.052906	0.0000

Effects Specification

	S.D.	Rho
Period random	0.000000	0.0000
Idiosyncratic random	0.064333	1.0000

Weighted Statistics

R-squared	0.253183	Mean dependent var	0.069176
Adjusted R-squared	0.240417	S.D. dependent var	0.071049
S.E. of regression	0.061922	Sum squared resid	0.448624
F-statistic	19.83247	Durbin-Watson stat	0.094185
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Unweighted Statistics

R-squared	0.253183	Mean dependent var	0.069176
Sum squared resid	0.448624	Durbin-Watson stat	0.094185

probability leverage is more than .05 hence we conducted to know which model is suitable we conducted Hausman test

Table: 6 Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test Equation: Untitled Test period random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random	1.355028	2	0.5079

** WARNING: estimated period random effects variance is zero. Period random effects test comparisons:

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
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LEVER	-0.059547	-0.052846	0.000043	0.3047
LOG01	-0.028039	-0.026947	0.000003	0.5043

Period random effects test equation: Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares Date: 10/17/24 Time: 22:48; Sample (adjusted): 3/01/2013
3/01/2024

Periods included: 12; Cross-sections included: 10; Total panel (balanced) observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.497770	0.083266	5.978079	0.0000
LEVER	-0.059547	0.029764	-2.000637	0.0480
LOG01	-0.028039	0.004743	-5.911874	0.0000

Effects Specification

Period fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.269698	Mean dependent var	0.069176
Adjusted R-squared	0.180132	S.D. dependent var	0.071049
S.E. of regression	0.064333	Akaike info criterion	-2.540212
Sum squared resid	0.438704	Schwarz criterion	-2.215005
Log likelihood	166.4127	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.408144
F-statistic	3.011180	Durbin-Watson stat	0.086690
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000853		

Hausman test answer the question. We state H_n &

H_a as the hypothesis as

H_n : The Radom Effect Model is appropriate

H_a : The Fixed Effect Model is appropriate

P value is <.05we reject H_n and accept H_a meaning that the fixed effect model is appropriatemodel

The paper clearly articulates that companies having higher ESG scores are better financialperformers.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Only ESG 100 Index top 10 companies are selected from March 2013 to 2024 marchESG values may not reflect true position of the organisation.

Other elements may also affect the financial performance of the organisation

SCOPE

Each organisation impact can be individually studied. More parameters can be added to ESG to analyse organisation more effectively.

In this paper it is examined the relationship between ESG companies and the financial performance of NSE listed companies from 2013 to 2024. It is found that the fixed effect model is appropriate model

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